

Transforming Energy Access Planning: Data Governance Plan for the Implementation of PowerMap

Reiss Niih Boafo, Energy Commission, Ghana
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Executive Summary

Key Findings

This data governance plan outlines the framework for PowerMap, a geospatial data collection platform developed by the Energy Commission of Ghana to address challenges in accessing accurate and timely data for energy planning. The plan establishes a robust governance structure, including roles and responsibilities, risk management strategies, and data quality assurance processes. PowerMap utilizes a relational database structure centered around a powermap table, enabling efficient querying and analysis of power infrastructure across regions and districts. Rigorous data cleaning and formatting processes, including automated checks and standardization, ensure data integrity. The integration of field-collected data with existing geospatial datasets strengthens the Commission's capacity for comprehensive energy access analysis.

Recommendations

1. Implement Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for improved data exchange with other government systems.
2. Develop a formal data-sharing agreement framework to govern information exchange with external partners.
3. Enhance metadata and documentation guidelines to ensure long-term data usability and understanding.
4. Explore machine learning algorithms for anomaly detection and predictive analysis as the system matures.
5. Investigate citizen science and crowdsourcing approaches to supplement data collection efforts, particularly in remote areas.
6. Rebuild PowerMap using Python to enhance scalability and stability.
7. Conduct regular reviews and updates of data governance policies and procedures to maintain system integrity and relevance.

1. Introduction

Access to accurate and timely geospatial data is critical for effective energy planning and policy formulation. In Ghana, where the Energy Commission serves as the sole technical regulator for electrical energy, one would expect seamless access to such data from utilities and other stakeholders. However, the reality has proven otherwise (Attieku, 2023). Delays in receiving requested data, or in some cases, a complete lack of response from utilities, have posed significant challenges for the Commission's policy and planning teams. Without current and reliable data, conducting thorough energy access analysis has become increasingly difficult.

1.1 Purpose

This data governance plan seeks to address the data access challenges by exploring the development and implementation of a geospatial data collection platform called PowerMap. The platform is designed to facilitate the collection of geospatial data for electrical facilities across Ghana, beginning with substations, transformers, and power plants. By enhancing data accuracy and availability, this initiative aims to improve the Commission's ability to perform effective inspections and strengthen overall data governance, ultimately transforming energy access in the country (Energy Commission, 2024).

1.2 Scope

This data governance plan applies to all geospatial and related data to be collected, stored, processed, and used by the Energy Commission of Ghana through the PowerMap.

It encompasses:

- Data collected by inspection and enforcement officers during field activities.
- Data collected by skilled teams recruited for comprehensive data gathering.
- All processes involved in data handling, including collection, storage, integration, analysis, dissemination, and archival.
- All personnel involved in data-related activities, including inspectors, data managers, analysts, IT staff, and decision-makers.
- All systems and technologies that will be used for data management, including the web application, databases, servers, and data visualization tools.

1.3 Objectives

The primary objectives of this Data Governance Plan are:

- **Ensure data quality:** Establish processes and standards to maintain high-quality, accurate, and reliable data.

- **Enhance data security and privacy:** Protect sensitive data from unauthorized access, breaches, and other security threats.
- **Facilitate data accessibility and sharing:** Enable seamless access to data for relevant stakeholders while maintaining appropriate access controls.
- **Support effective decision-making:** Use geospatial data to inform energy access planning, resource allocation, and policy development.
- **Promote collaboration:** Foster a collaborative environment among various teams within the Energy Commission through shared access to real-time data.
- **Establish compliance:** Adhere to all relevant legal, regulatory, and industry standards governing data management and privacy.

2. Methodology

2.1 Tools Implemented

As outlined in the introduction, the tool being implemented is PowerMap, developed using PHP and JavaScript. This tool includes a form designed to collect the following data:

- a. Name of the electrical facility
- b. Type of facility (e.g., transformer, power plant, or substation)
- c. Geolocation of the electrical facility (longitude and latitude)
- d. Capacity and output, depending on the facility type
- e. Circuit readings of the facility, applicable if it is a transformer or substation

Figure 1: Data collection form

2.2 Data Sources

Data will be collected from the following sources for the implementation of the PowerMap.

Table 1: Data sources listed for the implementation of PowerMap

Primary Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Field surveys conducted by Energy Commission inspection & enforcement officers • Real-time geospatial data on power facilities (transformers, substations, power plants) • Capacity readings and other critical measurements from on-site inspections
Secondary Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing Energy Commission databases • Ghana Grid Company (GRIDCo) infrastructure data • Electricity Company of Ghana (ECG) distribution network information
Open Data Platforms	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OpenStreetMap for base mapping • Ghana Statistical Service geospatial datasets • World Bank energy access indicators for Ghana

2.3 Assumptions

To ensure data integrity and accuracy, the following data governance framework, including its principles, roles, responsibilities and risk management measures, will be implemented. This framework is designed to guarantee the reliability and precision of the data.

a. Data Governance Principles

Table 2: List of data governance principles

No.	Principle	Definition
1	Accountability	Clear definition of roles and responsibilities for data management tasks.
2	Transparency	Open and clear communication about data processes and policies.
3	Integrity	Ensuring data accuracy and consistency throughout its lifecycle.
4	Security	Protecting data from unauthorized access and breaches.
5	Compliance	Adhering to all applicable laws, regulations, and standards.
6	Efficiency	Streamlining data processes to reduce redundancy and enhance productivity.
7	Collaboration	Encouraging cooperation among different directorates and stakeholders.

b. Roles & Responsibilities

Table 3: Assigned roles and responsibilities for implementation of PowerMap

No.	Team/Role	Composition/Personnel	Responsibilities
1	Data Governance Council	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Senior Manager, IT 2. Senior Manager, Electricity Enforcement 3. Deputy Director, Policy & Planning 4. Deputy Director, Legal 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Oversee the implementation of the Data Governance Plan. b. Approve data policies, standards, and procedures. c. Resolve data-related conflicts and issues. a. Review and update the governance framework periodically.
2	Web-app Developer	Senior Officer, HR & Admin.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Back-end b. Front-end interface c. Troubleshooting d. System integration
3	Database Designer and Security Officer	Assistant Manager, IT	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Ensuring data protection and security compliance. b. Implements and maintaining data encryption protocols c. Conducting regular security audits d. Managing access control for platform
4	Field Inspectors and Data Collectors	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Senior Officer, Electricity Enforcement 2. Officer, Electricity Enforcement 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Accurately collect and input data into the web application during inspections b. Ensure timely submission of collected data. c. Follow data collection guidelines and standards.

c. Risk Management

Table 4: Risk identification and mitigation

Category	Risk	Risk Level	Mitigation Strategy
Cybersecurity	Unauthorized access to sensitive power infrastructure	High	Quarterly internal security audits
Cybersecurity	Insider threats from employees or contractors	High	Continuous automated vulnerability scanning
Operational	Data loss/corruption during data synchronization process	High	Offsite storage of encrypted backup data
Legal	Non-compliance with Ghana's Data Protection Act	High	Establishment of computer security incident response team
Legal	Unauthorized sharing of sensitive infrastructure information	High	Detailed response plan development
Cybersecurity	Data interception during field collection activities	Medium	Annual third-party penetration testing
Operational	System downtime during critical inspection periods	Medium	Daily incremental backups, weekly full backups
Operational	Inaccurate data entry by field inspectors	Medium	Monthly disaster recovery drills

3. Results

3.1 Charts and Graphs

The design of a robust and scalable database is critical for efficiently managing and analyzing geospatial and infrastructure data related to power distribution.

Below is the database schema of the PowerMap. It consists of three main tables, namely

Figure 2: Database Schema

- a. **region:** Stores information about geographical regions.
- b. **district:** Contains data on districts within regions.
- c. **powermap:** Central table linking regions, districts, and power infrastructure.

The powermap table acts as a hub, connecting to the other tables through foreign key relationships. It includes details on various types of power infrastructure (transformers, substations, power plants) and their locations. The schema allows for tracking capacity, conditions, detailed circuit information for transformers, and capacity and output for power plants. Geospatial data (POLYGON and POINT types) is used to represent locations and areas.

This structure enables comprehensive management and analysis of a power distribution network across different geographical divisions.

3.2 Main Findings

The data collection strategy leverages the existing inspection processes of the Energy Commission while introducing new technologies and methodologies to enhance data accuracy, coverage, and timeliness. The combination of professional inspections and remote sensing provides a comprehensive approach to geospatial data collection for energy access planning in Ghana.

Table 5: Data Collection

No.	Data Collection Method	Description
1	Field Surveys	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Web app-based data collection by Energy Commission inspectors during routine site visits b. GNSS devices such as GPS will be used to capture precise locations of power facilities c. Standardized forms within the web application to ensure consistent data capture across inspectors
2	Remote Sensing	Satellite imagery analysis to identify large-scale power infrastructure in remote areas.

Incoming data will undergo rigorous cleaning, including automated range checks for numerical readings, standardization of units to megawatts (MW) & KVA, and spatial validation to ensure all recorded facilities are within Ghana's borders.

Table 6: Data Cleaning and Formatting

No.	Data Cleaning & Formatting Method	Description
1	Error Detection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Automated checks for out-of-range values in numeric fields (e.g., capacity, ratings) b. Spatial validation to ensure coordinates fall within Ghana's boundaries by satellite imagery to overlay the point location electrical facilities. c. Cross-referencing facility names and IDs against known lists to catch typos
2	Standardization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Conversion of all capacity measurements to a standard unit (e.g., MW, kVA) b. Normalization of enum fields (e.g., transformer condition) to predefined values c. Standardization of geographic coordinate system to Ghana's official projection
3	Validation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Cross-checking total capacities against known national or regional figures b. Verification of facility locations using satellite imagery c. Regular audits comparing database entries to physical inspection reports

4. Discussion

4.1 Insights and Results Implications

The development and implementation of the PowerMap database and data collection platform has several important implications for the Energy Commission of Ghana. The relational database structure, with the powermap table serving as the central hub, allows for efficient querying and analysis of power infrastructure data within specific geographic contexts.

This will enable the Commission to better understand the distribution and status of transformers, substations, and power plants across regions and districts, supporting more informed energy access planning and resource allocation.

The rigorous data cleaning and formatting processes, including automated checks, standardization, and validation, help ensure the accuracy, consistency, and reliability of the collected data. This will improve the Commission's ability to make data-driven decisions, as they can have confidence in the integrity of the information. The integration of field-collected data with existing geospatial datasets, such as administrative boundaries merged with population density maps, will further strengthen the Commission's capacity for comprehensive energy access analysis and policy development.

4.2 Potential Technologies/Areas Worth Exploration/Policy Recommendations

The implementation of Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) for data exchange with other government systems could improve interoperability and collaborative planning efforts.

From a policy perspective, the Commission will consider developing a formal datasharing agreement framework to govern the exchange of information with external partners, such as utility companies and other government agencies. This could help streamline the data acquisition process and ensure compliance with relevant regulations, such as Ghana's Data Protection Act.

4.3 Limitations of Study

The metadata and documentation guidelines, while essential for ensuring long-term data usability and understanding, may require more detailed development and enforcement to achieve the desired level of transparency and information sharing across the energy sector of Ghana.

4.4 Potential Areas for Future Research

As the PowerMap system matures, the Commission should explore opportunities for continuous improvement, such as the implementation of machine learning algorithms for anomaly detection and predictive analysis.

The current PowerMap is developed using PHP and JavaScript. The Commission plans to rebuild it using a Python script to enhance scalability and stability.

The Commission may also want to investigate the potential of citizen science and crowdsourcing approaches to supplement the data collection efforts, particularly in remote areas where field inspections may be challenging. This could involve engaging local communities and leveraging mobile devices to gather additional information and improve the overall coverage and timeliness of the geospatial data.

5. Conclusion

5.1 Recap and Lessons Learnt

The development of the PowerMap data collection platform is a significant step forward for the Energy Commission of Ghana in addressing the longstanding challenges of geospatial data accessibility and quality. By leveraging this application, the Commission will be able to establish a comprehensive geospatial database of power infrastructures. The rigorous data cleaning and integration processes will improve the reliability and usability of the information, enabling more informed decision-making and collaborative planning.

5.2 Recommendations

Going forward, the Commission should strengthen the data governance framework, to ensure the principles of accountability, transparency, and security are firmly embedded within the use of the system and the data collected. Regular reviews and updates to the policies and procedures governing data management are crucial to maintaining the integrity and relevance of the PowerMap system.

Additionally, the Commission should explore opportunities to expand the data collection efforts, potentially through citizen science initiatives and the integration of real-time sensor data. This would further enhance the Commission's understanding of the energy landscape and support the development of more targeted and effective policies to improve energy access across Ghana. The implementation of APIs for data exchange with other government systems could also improve interoperability and collaborative planning efforts.

6. References

1. Attieku, S. (2023). Access to energy facility GIS data. Accra, Ghana.
2. Energy Commission. (2024). Accra, Ghana.

